

Environmental Impact of Climate Change on National Security

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ABSTRACT

Today, different groups of activists have failed to improve the climate regime. Climate change and global warming are regarded as two factors, which play a significant role in threatening human security since food shortages, water scarcity, environmental degradation, poverty, disease outbreaks, and mass migration can separately lead to national security, which will undermine and contribute to the failed government scenario. In the domestic and global arena, the security of the modern government becomes meaningful with respect to superior power, and the society is considered insecure even if it faces with a lack of threats. In the modern national security discourse, we see an increase in security software, in addition to its hardware. The present study aimed to provide an analysis of the environmental impacts of climate change on national security in the context of international environmental law through a cross-disciplinary approach to international law and geopolitics.

INTRODUCTION

After World War II, national security was multi-dimensional, covering military, political, social, economic and environmental aspects. In the period from 1990 to 1990, national security was mostly "ideological and military," and its indicator was "Cold War," while in the period from 1990 to 2030, national security would be more affected by food security and environmental issues. And hungry and unemployed people will often be relocated to national and international borders. The global water crisis also threatens the security of the world and has transformed the concept of national security. It has been argued that environmental issues from 1950 to 2030 are divided into two periods: 1. Economic (1950-1990) and 2-ecological (1990-2030). Climate change can spark global instability, hunger, poverty and conflict, and exacerbate water and food shortages, infectious diseases, and tensions on resources and the number of natural disasters. Climate change is a threat to national (domestic) security of all countries, especially developing countries, and low-lying island states such as Cribatti, Marshall Islands and the

Maldives, which by the end of this century may be totally uninhabitable and also cause internal conflicts, especially in countries with weak governments such as Darfur, where disputes related to land and available water are more common if adaptive programs are not set up to deal with the consequences mentioned. Climate change in Iran has been associated with an increase in atmospheric anomalies such as sudden and severe flooding, heavy snowfall in hot and cold places, reduced rainfall in humid and mountainous areas, an increase in the average temperature of some cities, and a massive drought. Because Iran is in a dry belt and irregular use of water and a one-dimensional view of development in agricultural and industrial sectors, the status of water is in serious danger. This is in addition to the micro-thunder storms, especially in the south and west of Iran, and at the risk of having many lakes, wetlands and rivers from Zayandeh Rood, Hirmand, to the Lake Hamoon to the Karoon, the Shadegan Lagoon and Lake Urmia, causing humans forced to move.

Result and Discussion

1. Environmental security, international commitments to climate change and the challenge of climate security

The emergence of global environmental problems, such as global warming and the loss of the ozone layer, has been one of the first attempts to secure the environment on a worldwide scale. Brunslind's report (1980) stated that "little threat to the peace and survival of the human community will have a more severe impact than the threats posed by the increasing and irreversible degradation of the biosphere that human life depends on." (Brauch, 2003) These new threats reflect the need to redefine the nature of security in a world that relied on each other and continues to face new challenges.

In the post-Cold War era, the environmental security dialogue opened the door for discussion on a common approach to security matters. For example, in December 1988 at the United Nations General Assembly, Gorbachev emphasized that "the relationship between man and the environment has become a threatening relationship. The threat from the sky is no longer a rocket launch, but global warming". (Myers, 1993) He also presented the idea of establishing an Environmental Security Council. Following these requests for security, several initiatives took place in the early post-Cold War period.

Concerns about climate change not only led to the creation of an Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) to assess the scientific, technical and socio-economic aspects of human impact on climate change, but also the signing of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change in Rio was followed in 1992. Negotiations on climate change, however, were more complicated than ozone-depleted negotiations, because action on climate change requires a significant shift in the economic and lifestyle structures. Hence, climate change has been marginalized and discarded in environmental security discourse.

Environmental disruption has various consequences such as soil erosion, reduced biodiversity, pollution of water, soil, air, etc. Based on this in the contemporary world, low carbon economy is considered as one of the essential ways for sustainable development and reduction of environmental pollution. Low-carbon economy or low-fossil economics is said to be the economy that produces

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the lowest "greenhouse gas." One of the most critical greenhouse gas emissions is carbon dioxide emissions due to the use of fossil fuels on the Earth's surface.

The excessive increase in pollutant emissions is a significant cause of global warming and climate change. It is clear that by reducing the consumption of fossil fuels and relying on new sources of energy (clean energy), such as wind energy and solar energy, it is possible to prevent the emission of pollutants primarily. The low carbon economy, besides being one of the ways to deal with global climate change, can be an excellent alternative to these sources, given the prediction of non-renewable resources in oil countries. Therefore, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Kyoto Protocol have broadly sought to root out the potential negative impacts of concentrated energy activity in the atmosphere; climate change is based on the principle of prevention, the anticipation of future fluctuations in water and air and regulates and formulate policies for responding to these works. Given the link between the world economy and the current climate and the current recession in the world, it has provided an opportunity to work for a low-carbon economy. (Ranganathan, 2004)

Iran has also devised a Low-Carbon Economy Development Program for its macroeconomic policy agenda.¹

1-1 Environmental Security

Environmental disruption has various consequences such as soil erosion, reduced biodiversity, pollution of water, soil, air, etc. Despite the initial determination and wide range of environmental security discourses, discussions on this issue took place through talks on environmental disputes. This has also helped frame environmental threats to become more familiar with the conditions of national security experts, and also helped to address the environment as a reasonable and justifiable threat. The issue of environmental security has shown that there are two tendencies. The first approach emphasizes the impact

¹. On June 11, 2014, the government commissioned the Industrial and Environmental Infrastructure Commission, with the participation of all relevant organizations, to develop a national development plan for a low-carbon economy in line with the economic policies of the resistance, and to approve it by the Cabinet of Ministers.

of the national security discourse on focusing on the subject of conflict, which threatens the environment and those dependent on them as a threat to the order and global stability, and other aspects, such as health effects and over-consumption problems, have been mainly ignored. At the same time, this discourse has challenged a series of security measures focusing on military threats and reactive actions and emphasized the extent to which military preparedness and response to address environmental issues are inadequate. However, it has helped to shift attention to various types of vulnerabilities, which indicates that the tools needed to ensure stability requires efforts to promote both the reduction of environmental changes and adaptation and that the best results are accompanied by instructive and preventive measures and emphasize the importance of the relocation problem. This indicates that disasters or conflicts in a region have the potential to affect the homeless and the displacement of people, other areas and countries. The second tendency emphasizes local integration, which increases the flexibility of local housing. It highlights the increase in diversity and choice and supports the existence of those relationships and institutions that are capable of managing settlements. This discourse reflects environmental values and considerations such as diversity and flexibility that are threatened by unsustainable development. It represents a more comprehensive and ecological view of the security problem, which considers overseas threats as part of a broader security ecology. This does not deny those power relationships that are in the process of security. On the contrary, this shows that other forms of power, such as the argumentative and symbolic forms used in environmental discourse, have played an essential role in defining a less controversial approach to security.

These two aspects, one influenced by reactive and defensive actions, and others inspired by precautionary and preventive measures, are balanced mainly in the context of environmental security discourse in Western countries. For example, the European Union has traditionally emphasized a more proactive approach than a reactive approach. As a result, various security arrangements for environmental issues have led security measures to be primarily influenced by activities that have been undertaken in the environmental sector to ensure safety, adaptability and flexibility. In this context, those "emergency measures" that have been raised due to ecological protection requests

are designed and developed in the context of current political debate. (Dalby, 2012)

1-2 International obligations in the face of climate change

Soft law refers to sources that are not binding and do not have specific enforcement guarantees, including statements, resolutions, agendas, action plans, and so on. Their primary purpose is to express the principles and rules of government action. Although these sources are not binding in themselves, they have a very significant impact on the development of international environmental law. The most important of these are the Stockholm Declaration of 1972 on Human and Environment, the Universal Declaration of Nature, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly in 1982, as well as the 1992 Rio Declaration, which has had a great deal of influence in this field. (Poorhashemi, 2011)

Relevant international treaties on climate change are:

(A) The Stockholm Declaration, (B) the Rio Conference or Summit (this summit and previous sessions resulted in the ratification of the Kyoto Protocol Framework and Protocol), (C) the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change and the Meeting of the Parties, (D) the Kyoto Protocol, (E) Copenhagen Summit; (F) Paris Summit, Paris Agreement (COP21).

1-3. Climate Security Challenge

The issue of environmental security has been marginalized as a result of the war on terrorist activity. The fight against terrorist activities has made other threats more urgent and more severe than environmental risks. Nevertheless, over the last few years, concerns over climate change have taken a decisive step forward. Several factors have contributed to this new progress: on the one hand, there has been an increasing consensus on the various aspects of the impact of human activities on the climate; On the other hand, since the exit of the

United States of America from the Kyoto Protocol, several "security measures" have been taken to promote measures to address climate change and its consequences, which has been on both sides of the Atlantic.

Climate safety is a concern for climate security, which is considered to be a prerequisite for all humanitarian actions in terms of maintaining a stable climate, not merely the safety of the water and air is to be considered. Climate safety is created to protect the people and communities that depend on it. As the issue of environmental protection, climate security is about "keeping the levels of civilization." (Buzan, 1991) It raises the problem and identifies two opposing approaches to security regulations. The first approach, relying on emergency measures, shows that preparedness for all potential threats is not possible, and it is best to address them when emergencies occur; the second approach is to take preventive measures that will inform about potentially catastrophic effects. This means that the exchange of security is the shift from one position to another. This change is evident in the discussion of the type of threats posed by climate change and its recent transformations. There are two aspects to this transformation. First, many talks have been shaped in terms of adaptation to climate change, assuming that this is a slow process. It is implicit in the UNFCCC, which states that the purpose of the Convention is to achieve a stabilization of the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, which prevents human intervention in climate systems. Such attention should be completed within a reasonable period of time so that ecosystems can adapt to climate change naturally to ensure that food production is not threatened and that economic development can be sustained.

This discourse takes into account the relative stability of the climate systems. Constant changes occur in a predictable way and rely on the ability of human adaptability and innovation. The likelihood of catastrophic events has challenged this approach. This

means that when a sophisticated system reaches its peak, it can have nasty responses that will result in uncontrollable changes that are difficult to re-control. Examples of such catastrophic events can be the disturbance of the gulf stream, the weakening of the monsoon rainfalls and the instability of the continental ice layers. The recent security movement relied on the remarkable continuity of this threat. The second aspect is the change in the importance of the two different security and sharing arrangements.

The first security measure considers climate change as a threat. The second security measure views environmental policies as a threat. The latter case was evident in the United States' position at the Earth Summit in 1992 when George W. Bush stated that "American lifestyle is not going to be negotiated." (Lerner, 1998) The United States subsequently withdrew from the Kyoto Protocol, which was considered a threat to the US economy. This kind of security is also evident in the concerns expressed by some developing countries, which is indicative of the opposition to the implementation of policies aimed at forcing them to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions because such systems can threaten their development. The review of climate change economics, prepared by Nicholas Stern's economist for the British government and released in October 2006, is an intervention in this debate and has been instrumental in securing climate change rather than securing environmental policies. Stern's review focused on the economic implications of climate change, an aspect that has often been marginalized in the context of environmental safety discourse, and also emphasized the financial cost of the suspension of action. Thus, the idea that environmental effect can be a threat to competitiveness and economic growth is subject to cost-benefit analysis, which warned that neglect and failure to take action on climate change could affect the global economy between 5% up to 20% of global gross domestic product per year, while the cost of reducing greenhouse gas emissions to prevent the

worst effects of climate change can be limited to around 1% of global gross domestic product annually. Stern explores the characteristics of the difference between a European approach that tends to focus on environmental policy as an opportunity, and the US approach that puts it a potential threat.

As has been shown so far, threats not only identify the benefits and values that are supposed to be protected, but also demonstrate security-related practices and principles. Hence, it is relevant to examine which specific aspects are identified in the climate security discourse, to assess the capabilities and constraints of a transformation process. The list of threats posed by Margaret Beckett, the former British foreign secretary, is illustrative and explanatory. She focused on food security, water issues, the security of energy supply, migration, conflicts and unsuccessful governments and stated that "bad weather means more unsuccessful governments."

However, this focus has two problematic issues. Firstly, it aims to sum up the sustainability problem in a greenhouse gas issue, creating a false impression that was focusing solely on reducing greenhouse gas emissions or shifting consumption to non-greenhouse gas, such as nuclear fuel or fuel Bio, which is enough to solve the environmental crisis. This approach, the complexity of ecological problems, and the over-consumption of limited resources are of less importance. But climate change is only one aspect of the broader shift of human activities to the environment. As humans put pressure on the planet's capacity to sustain, the climate change problem is rising, especially for those who live in peripheral and vulnerable areas. Reducing greenhouse gas emissions will not solve all other environmental issues or increase the flexibility of vulnerable groups. About the Katrina hurricane, although, this phenomenon has been associated with global warming, it's devastating impact is also a result of other local problems, such as lagging water losses or underground mining; issues with the design and maintenance standards of the harbour; the weakness of emergency services focused

on other security priorities. There is a secure link between the focus on reducing greenhouse gas emissions and focus on improving flexibility and compatibility. In this way, the focus on greenhouse gas emissions is to narrow the overall vision proposed by environmental safety.

The second is the link between climate security and energy security. This link has an inherent tension because the security of energy is traditionally linked to national security and its logic. In contrast, climate security is supposed to improve a collaborative approach to global issues. Energy-related agreements are generally the result of bilateral agreements between governments. The energy sector forms a significant part of the government's revenue and policy. Governments earn incomes from licenses, shipping, and taxes, or operate directly with national companies. Therefore, the current situation is characterized by inadequate energy markets, with features such as increased demand, high prices and worries about terrorist attacks against critical infrastructure, which is especially challenging for governments, which both want to promote privatization and call for partnership mostly divided into energy policies.

The resumption of the debate on climate change and security seems to be an attempt to turn it into an existing threat, requiring urgent action. It has mobilized political action, emergency measures and even attempts to institutionalize this debate internationally. (Mazinianian, 2017) So far, demands for climate security have mobilized efforts, although emergency measures have not exceeded the current political debates. Therefore, these requests can be considered as proper security, not as unsuccessful security movements. Climate change security has avoided the identification of enemies, along with governments, actors and actors, both in the security movement and security regulations. Another aspect related to the climate security discourse is the security of those threats that are uncertain and wide-ranging, and their impact assessment is difficult; this is one of

the applications of the "precautionary approach through prevention" approach that can be made to security. (Beck, 2006) The possibility of becoming a threat to the still unfulfilled nature and prescribing the proposed methods by the Copenhagen group regarding security is a vague vision. The probable admission of a precautionary approach to security issues has been criticized for these reasons, which could justify a preventive military operation, extensive oversight measures, reversing the burden of proof or making decisions at worst.

Concerning the environment, the security of climate change may lead to conflicting policies, and governments will adopt policies to protect their territory against rising sea levels and immigration, and the Security Council adopts resolutions about the emission of greenhouse gases, and even military action against contaminated plants; and monitoring systems to control the emission of greenhouse gases. However, it will depend on the decision to accept security logic based on enemies and extraordinary actions.

What is being discussed in the context of climate security is the possibility of introducing mechanisms to prevent emergencies in a system that relies on emergency management and, on the other hand, relies on insurance and compensation. Climatic security is an attempt to stimulate the symbolic power of an environmental discourse that relies on interdependence and prevention to provide a framework for controlling security and energy globally. This is related to the re-negotiation of spaces in which risk management and trading mechanisms are prevalent, and the spaces in which intervention and regulation are accepted. Security is still a significant part of the political process. Its consequences depend to a great extent on what is being secured and what security tools are used. (Tayebi, 2017)

4. Effects of Climate Change in Iran

It is often thought as the Middle East has meagre water resources and dry weather; the impact of climate change could be negligible. The water resources in the area are under intense and increasing pressure. Any change in weather patterns that increase the temperature and reduce rainfall, greatly enhance existing problems. In this region, wars have been projected over water for more than a decade. (Wolf and Others, 2015)

Water, like oil, across the Middle East, is a strategic commodity that is surplus in some countries, and some states are in short supply. Water is also a vital public (for drinking) and an indispensable input for many industrial and agricultural products. Water is also a common source that requires collaborative management to the fullest. The changes in our country are more prevalent in the form of rainfall reduction, temperature rise, long-term droughts, flood events, and turbulence of the regime, with increasing inconsistency among the catchment areas of the country. In the world, 30 percent of the surface water flow is environmentally water rights, but this figure is 10 percent in Iran, and the same amount has been declining over the past decade. Experts say that drying up wetlands will cost \$ 16 billion annually to the country. (Wolf, and Others, 2015) When the social, economic, political, environmental and military phenomena endanger the security and stability of the society, the political system, national solidarity and territorial integrity of a country, which could not be controlled and governed by existing rules and regulations, the phenomenon comes into the security domain. This means that the aspect in public opinion is so threatened that its elimination justifies the use of any means of force.

Meanwhile, tracking rainfall incident-related events in the country indicates that any change in the amount of rainfall, whether increasing or decreasing, results in significant damage in the form of floods and droughts. It is clear the environment has no borders.

Based on this fact, all countries in the world should cooperate for environmental protection. (Khalatbari & Poorhashemi, 2019)

Moreover, during this time, most of the country's regions have suffered from the damage caused by these two factors. Based on the findings of our country, the destruction of vegetation, the capture of rivers and the change in land use in the emergence of floods and the influx of waterways have played a fundamental role. Available data and documents suggest that the more extensive the vegetation is, the less soil erosion. Over the last six decades, of the 25 million hectares of forest, only 14 million hectares remain. Current estimates indicate that 70 square meters of the country's forests are destroyed per second. Based on this, the flood event is the natural consequence of the processes. As we assume that the flood is a surplus runoff on the river's capacity, it can reduce the ability of the river whenever it is taken to any stream, and, in response to the volume of water in the form of massive floods with lots of financial and psychological damage, especially to the river bed structures. Rising from the flood event, many infrastructure and structures in the water, electricity and agriculture sectors, livestock of the villagers, settlements, fields, crooked roads, roads of pride, deviators, farms and livestock breeding are severely damaged. (Kaviani, 2016)

4-1. Dust

In recent decades, the development of cities, the development of technology in the industrialized world and the changing climate and the occurrence of continuous and prolonged droughts, air pollution is a growing trend, and dust² are considered as one of the

². Dust is a small suspended particle, both solid and liquid, found in the air. This type of air pollution includes any floating material in the air. These particles and floating materials include dust and smoke and particles visible to other fine micro-particles. The content of these particles varies from gravel sand to various metals, depending on the geography of the site and the characteristics of the soils and the geographical environment.

air pollutants. One of the air pollutions that we have seen in recent years in the West, Southwest and most recently in Iran is the dust phenomenon. This phenomenon, due to climate change and because of rain shortage and drought in the most desert areas of most countries in the world, such as Iraq, Saudi Arabia, Iran, Pakistan, occurs in the warm seasons and can be called as a natural process, in recent years, due to the proliferation of deserts and human activities that caused the drying of wetlands and lakes and the displacement of a massive mass of soil in Iraq, Syria and Saudi Arabia, it created substantial airborne pollution in the Wide dust areas of Iran, especially the west and southwest. (Karim Rousta, Ardebili, 2010) In general, the factors affecting the generation and distribution of dust phenomena include climate change, low rainfall and drought, surface water containment, soil moisture content, severe winds on deserts with soft soils, and so on. In addition to direct economic effects of dust, its indirect effects include the migration of citizens from areas exposed to storms in other cities or even abroad, increasing population density in cities, losing job opportunities, filling channels watering and raising dredging costs, forced holidays in cities and shortening office hours. The mental problems caused by the microbes, the polluted air and the inappropriate appearance of towns, the closure of the commercial project, production, service, and the resulting psychological problems. The microscopes also affect the health of humans and cause heart and respiratory illnesses (Memarian Fard, 2015).

4-2. water crisis

Iran is located on the dry belt of the planet and naturally has little rainfall. The same low rainfall is also highly dispersed and heterogeneous in terms of time and place. The available findings on precipitation show that due to climate change, the volume of rain that was scattered throughout the year has grown today, within a few days, it is tight and heavy. Most of the rainfall is flooded and plagued by plenty of damage from the area. However, if there is

not enough rainfall during the year, with such a volume of precipitation, it will face shortages in the coming months in a few days. On the other hand, the existing infrastructure and environmental culture of the community have not been harmonized due to such transformations. Experts believe that land-use change, the lack of synchronized planning and the use of unskilled methods in exploiting watersheds have created the ground for the frequent and increasing flood events, including landless use, construction continuity. In the bedding of the rivers, pouring of debris in the bed and by the rivers, disturbance of the ecological balance of the basins and eventually increasing the possibility of flood watersheds in the form of destruction of residential units and other structures. (Memarian Fard, 2015)

The components of "shortage" and "need" in the emergence of power relations and direction have a fundamental role for them. Available data show that over the past few decades, there have been phenomena such as climate change on a global scale and a change in rainfall pattern on a regional level; countries that previously had dry and mild weather have reduced precipitation as a result of excessive withdrawal from Groundwater resources, drop-in aquifers, and land subsidence. Based on these data, the world is going to dry. On the one hand, this phenomenon has led to the spread of social and national tensions and transnational scales with increasing tensions with its neighbors over the rivers and rivers. In the meantime, countries in the dry world are in a worse situation. For example, Iran is more vulnerable than other countries, with more than eighty-five percent of its groundwater resources being over, and water consumption has been increasing due to the inefficiency of consumption patterns and population growth. The fundamental challenge is that there is no bluer in many places or over the next few years. The fact is that the environmental crisis has not yet been put on the agenda of public appeals and demands. (Kaviani, 2016) About 95 percent of our country's water resources are submerged due to the

dry and semi-arid climate, and less than 5 percent of the water resources are flowing on the Earth. In the case of rainwater harvesting, it is possible to supply water in the next, but about 95% of groundwater is not the case.

As a result of several decades of inefficiency in management in the water and agriculture sector, the situation is such that Iran is at the top of the country with the highest rates of harvesting of renewable water resources. Hence, agriculture is false and inefficient in most parts of the country. However, it continues, which has led to 4 billion cubic meters of groundwater annually pumping, and 90 percent of it with a negligible 30 percent consumption. Agriculture will reach. The productivity that was supposed to be achieved to 40% by the end of the fifth development plan. On the other hand, due to the overlapping duties of the custodians and numerous brokers of the water sector, no organization or ministry deals specifically with the issue of water.

The most fundamental criterion for determining the degree of dryness in a region is the relationship between annual rainfall and the ability to evaporate the environment. Whatever the amount of precipitation is less than the evaporation capacity, the degree of dryness of that area is higher. In Iran, except for the boundaries of the Caspian Sea, in other regions, the ability to evaporate is far beyond rainfall. Over the past decade, the average rainfall in most cases was less than 250 mm. For example, the Blueberries 95-94, which were 231 mm in conformance with the last few years, when the precipitation was relatively good, was reported. The increasing global warming has led to further evaporation of water in the country. Based on current forecasts, in the coming years, the temperature of the country will increase by two degrees, which means more than 27 billion cubic meters of water is evaporated. This rate has increased by nearly 1.1 degrees over the last few years, which means freshwater resources in the country, which increases with the passing of each passing year and the increase

in the trend of global warming over the depth and extent of water in the country.

Meanwhile, due to population growth, urbanization, a modest approach to development, the inefficiency of consumption patterns, especially in the agricultural sector, the country's water reserves have been completed. For example, the global average per capita consumption of water is 170 cubic meters. In comparison, it is 590 cubic meters in Iran, a situation in which the Earth subsided in half of the country's plains. During this period, many lakes and wetlands such as Hooralazim, Orumieh, Bakhtegan, Parishan, Hamoon, Jazmoryan, Tashak and Maharloo have been extinct, and the country's largest rivers such as Karun and Zayandehrud have been turned off.

Strategists today are co-sponsoring the issue of water security in Southwest Asia, which covers the Iranian plateau, which is one of the fundamental challenges that will undermine the protection of the governments in these areas. Based on available reports, lack of water resources, successive droughts, and water management inefficiency, have turned water issue into one of the most critical dimensions of the Iranian environmental crisis, which will become more and more promising shortly. The same data shows that according to the current population growth rate, the population of Iran will reach 105 million by 2025, which means a deficit of tens of billions of cubic meters. Such a situation has led to the flow of water into the security sector in our country. Based on the axes provided by the secretary of the Supreme National Security Council, almost all the metropolises of Iran, especially Tehran, are on the list. Due to the lack of water, the ecosystems of the other country are unable to maintain the population. The analysis of the current situation suggests that from now on, hydro-political will be the basis of Iran's foreign policy, and the strategic depth of our country will follow the outsourcing of water resources.

Conclusion

Governance, as the essential concept and the central axis of modern state theory, implies the state's exclusive right to use force or legitimate power, which, on the one hand, seeks the acquisition of power and internal power and, on the other hand, seeks to gain international independence and authority. Therefore, in the domestic and the global arena, the security of the modern state becomes meaningful when it comes to superior power, and even if it is faced with a lack of threats, the insecure society is considered. In the modern national security discourse, we are witnessing the addition of security software in addition to its hardware. By reaching the peak of insecurity as a result of the sovereignty of a conscious attitude, the modern notion of national security was formed, which was based on a positive aspect and its foundation. They sought to develop the concept of security, and in particular, the development of a range of national security threats, critics argued that civilian threats such as environmental and economic threats could, in turn, be as dangerous as military threats, and therefore these threats should also be addressed as security threats. Non-traditional security threats are diverse, but there are many standard features in them. First, these threats are not primarily state-centered; they originate from agents or actors that are essentially in-country or transnational. Second, these challenges do not have a specific geographic location. If, in the past, the threat was of military powers in other countries, places or areas were determined for measures to contain that threat. A necessary prerequisite for security was the creation and maintenance of a military balance in strategic areas. But non-traditional challenges involve dispersed, multi-dimensional, and multi-strain risks. These challenges should be viewed in an inclusive and territorial way. Third, these challenges could not be limited to traditional defence policies alone. Defence or military organizations may play a role, especially when violent conflicts take place. Still, effective control and management of these challenges

require a range of civilian approaches, and analyzes have shown that these challenges threaten both individuals and governments.

As a result, the effects of climate change can create the chances of success and progress in the region; climate change, a shared threat that is not like any other threat, encourages countries to cooperate despite the existence of political and their ideological cooperation. By doing so, climate change can be a tool for friendly relations and peacebuilding. Adopting any specific adaptation action requires investment, institutional reform, and capacity building. Organizational improvements need to strengthen the institutions, correct the inefficiencies of the market to show environmental damage or resource cuts, and promote awareness and public participation. Capacity building is vital for controlling and reducing impacts on water quality. In addition to technical adaptation measures, improvement of management systems (synchronization of river basin use, transfer between basins, etc.) and development of drought and flood event planning to minimize the impact of climate change on water resources needed.

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